

INTERNAL ENVIRONMENTAL ANALYSIS IN HEALTH INSTITUTIONS**Selami Yıldırım***Doctor, Azerbaijan State University of Economics, Department of Business***Abstract**

Health institutions operate in a sector where uncertainty and change are extremely intense. In addition, health institutions are in fierce competition with other rival health institutions. In fact, the fierce competition between these health institutions today is referred to as hyper-competition. Health institutions can only survive and emerge successful from this fierce competition by developing evidence-based and implementable strategies. The first requirement for developing evidence-based and implementable strategies is to be able to carry out the proper internal environment analysis. In this study, we examine the functional sub-systems used in internal environment evaluation and important functional sub-system factors. Furthermore, we discuss approaches to the functional sub-system groups that form the basis of internal environment analysis in health institutions with the current examples.

Keywords: Internal Environment Analysis, Internal Environmental Approaches, Internal Environmental Analysis in Health Institutions

Introduction

Health institutions operate in a dynamic and changing environment. The shifts in needs and expectations of society, the increase in service costs, the expansion of cost-saving measures by insurance institutions such as Social Security Institution (SSI), and the intensification of competition in the healthcare sector have increased the need for strategic management in hospitals and other health institutions.

Internal environment analysis in health institutions is about identifying the institution's strengths and weaknesses through unveiling and evaluating the institutional data and information and making comparisons with other health institutions in the sector. Comparison with the rival institutions based on comprehensive internal environment analysis can help determine the institution's position compared to other health institutions and detect which activities the institution should improve, which activities it should start, and which activities it should stop to improve the institution's performance and be more competitive.

Internal environment consists of factors that are within the control of the institution and that directly impact its operations and performance. More importantly, internal factors help institutions to both defend themselves against threats and take advantage of opportunities arising from the external environment. These factors include management skills, human resources, financial resources, marketing capabilities, clinical systems, organizational structure, physical resources, corporate culture, and information systems.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to contribute to the literature on the internal environment analysis in health institutions. Furthermore, we aim to elaborate on the importance of specifying the functional sub-systems

and their interrelationships in carrying out internal environmental analysis in health institutions. For this purpose, we examine the important factors that make up the sub-systems used in the internal environmental evaluation.

A thorough internal environmental analysis requires a comprehensive discussion of how the main factors of sub-systems are classified. Therefore, we provide an extensive assessment of approaches employed in grouping the factors of sub-systems. We focus on practical approaches such as the analyses of resources, capabilities, institutional functions, and performance by providing comprehensive examples.

Methodology

In accordance with the purpose of the study, we conduct a detailed and systematic review of the related literature on internal environment analysis in health institutions. We provide a general assessment of the main findings of the literature regarding internal environment analysis techniques that are thought to be usable by health institutions. In addition, we try to enrich theoretical discussions with recent practical examples.

Internal environment analysis: conceptual framework

Health institution managers do not develop strategies based solely on information about external factors. As shown in Figure 1, managers also utilize information about the internal environment of the health institution in the process of developing strategies and making decisions. Unlike the external environment, the internal environment of health institutions contains institutional characteristics (human resources, finance, technology, goods and services supplied, and organizational structure) that are under the control of managers.

Figure 1. Environmental Analysis and Strategic Information-Input

The main purpose of internal environment analysis is to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the health institution. The strengths of a health institution are the institutional characteristics that make it different from its competitors, give it an advantage in competition, and enable it to achieve its goals.

The identification of the strengths and weaknesses of the health institution and their assessment in terms of the opportunities and threats created by the external environment constitute one of the critical stages of strategic management. By using tools (such as SWOT analysis) that enable the simultaneous analysis of the threats and opportunities created by the environment with the strengths and weaknesses of the institution, managers can develop more realistic/implementable strategies. The identification of the strengths and weaknesses of the business also guides managers about whether the strategies are implementable. Yet, it must be emphasized that certain tools, resources, skills, and abilities are required for the implementation of each strategy (Forgang, 2004:7). The motives and objectives of internal environment analysis can be listed as follows (Campbell, Stonehouse, Houston, 2002:31-32):

- Reviewing the current resources of the institution,
- Determining the fundamental and general skills that need to be developed or used,
- Evaluating the organizational and design form of value-creating activities,
- Identifying institutional weaknesses that will make it more difficult to implement strategies in the future,

- Assessing the performance of services (quantity and quality of services provided, cost, profit margin, etc.),
- Measuring the financial performance of the institution and comparing it with competitors,
- Determining potential areas for investment, and
- Assessing the suitability of the selected strategies.

When developing strategy in health institutions, the most important thing to consider is the feasibility of the strategies.¹⁷ Strategies that are not applicable will only reflect general intentions and expectations and will not provide guidance on how to achieve the desired results. To develop feasible strategies, it is a must to consider the resources that the health institution possesses. It is not possible to implement a strategy developed without considering the current or potential resources of the institution (Evans, et al. 2003:273). For instance, a hospital may aim to provide pediatric cardiology services as a part of a diversification strategy. However, if the hospital building is inadequate, there is no pediatric cardiologist in the hospital, or it is difficult to employ a specialist due to lack of resources, this diversification strategy will not be possible to implement.

Whyte and Blair (1995) propose that in order to easily perform an internal environment analysis, a health institution should be split up into ten functional sub-systems, and these sub-systems should be analyzed first individually and then in relation to each other based on their interactions. Table 1 summarizes the sub-systems proposed by Whyte and Blair (1995) and the factors that should be considered during the analysis process.

¹⁷ Evans, et al. (2003:270) argue that four criteria must be considered in the development and evaluation of a strategic choice. These criteria are: (i) *suitability*, the ease with which the strategy helps achieve the goals, (ii) *feasibility*, applicability of the strategy with the current resources, (iii) *acceptability*, appropriateness of the strategy for the strategic groups

such as the board of directors and shareholders, and (iv) *competitive advantage*, that is, the strategy should serve to raise the competitiveness of the institution and position it better than its competitors.

Table 1.

Sub-Systems used in the Assessment of Internal Environment	
Sub-Systems	Factors Considered in the Analysis Process
Management	Number of management levels, management skills, delegation of authority, and centralization.
Human Resources	Number and quality of personnel, personnel recruitment options, personnel productivity, and personnel turnover.
Finance	Adequacy of financial resources, financial performance indicators, and deviations from budget.
Marketing	Attributes of current patients (insurance, severity of the disease, demographics), patient referral sources, utilization rates, and service delivery channels.
Clinical Systems	Amount and quality of services provided, medical technology used, and implementation of new treatment methods.
Institutional Structure	Rules and procedures in the relationships among institutional departments and programs.
Institutional Culture	Value systems, behavioral expectations, and characteristics.
Physical Resources	Adequacy of the buildings and physical expansion opportunities.
Information Systems	Effectiveness of clinical, administrative, and financial information systems.
Leadership	Leadership styles of top, middle, and lower level managers.

As depicted in Figure 2, the analyses of the sub-systems given in Table 1 can be classified into four groups:

- Analysis of resources,
- Analysis of capabilities,
- Analysis of organizational functions, and
- Performance analysis.

Figure 2. Sub-System Groups

Resource analysis: resource based strategy approach

One of the approaches in connection with strategic management is the resource-based strategy approach. The resource-based strategic approach focuses on the resources and capabilities of the health institution during the strategic development process. While the focus

of the environmental (market-oriented) approach is the environmental conditions, the starting point of the resource-based approach is the institutional resources. In other words, the market-oriented strategic approach is an outside-in strategy, while the resource-based approach is an inside-out strategy. On the other hand, both

the market-oriented and resource-based strategic approaches aim to achieve competitive advantage. The market-oriented strategic approach targets to achieve competitive advantage by shielding against environmental threats and taking advantage of environmental

opportunities, while the resource-based approach, as shown in Figure 3, assumes that the health institution can achieve competitive advantage through its own resources and capabilities, that is, through its strengths (Barney, 1991).

Figure 3. Market-oriented and Resource-based Strategic Approaches

Source: Adapted from Barney (1991) and Luke, et al. (2004:32).

Institutional resources are assets that a health institution owns and can control their uses (Pegels, Rogers, 1986:36). The assets of an institution (asset portfolio) consist of tangible resources (such as buildings, equipment, and financial resources) and human resources (institutional personnel), and intangible resources (such as patents and copyrights) and capabilities (such as corporate culture, core competencies, general competencies, and institutional prestige and recognition) (Wheelen, Hunger, 2012:137; Fahy, Smithee, 1999).

According to the resource-based strategy approach, for a firm to gain a competitive advantage and improve its economic performance (e.g., its profit), its resources and capabilities must have four key attributes, abbreviated as VRIO (Barney, Clark, 2007:57-69).

- **Valuableness:** In order for a resource or capability to be considered valuable, it must contribute to the implementation of strategies aiming to improve the productivity and performance of the health institution. In other words, for resources and capabilities to be valuable, they must ensure that the health institution is protected against environmental threats and benefits from environmental opportunities. For example, the Başkent University Hospital is considered one of the best organ transplant centers in the world. Two of its most important resources and capabilities establishing this competitive advantage in organ transplant services are

undoubtedly its transplantation team and their experience.

- **Rarity:** For a resource to provide a competitive advantage, the resource must be scarce, that is, rare. Resources that can be easily accessed or used by all institutions cannot provide a competitive advantage. We can clarify the matter by focusing on organ transplant services. The number of surgeons with high experience in organ transplantation in Turkey is low. Due to the low number of surgeons with experience in transplantation, hospitals with experienced surgeons will naturally have a greater competitive advantage over their rivals. On the other hand, to provide services in the field of organ transplantation, not only an experienced medical team, but also facilities with outstanding technological equipment such as tissue typing laboratories are required. However, the use of advanced technologies also requires an immense amount of investment (financial resources). Therefore, advanced technological opportunities are also considered rare/scarce resources because not every health institution can use them.

- **Inimitability:** If the resources of a health institution cannot easily be imitated, these resources provide the institution with a competitive advantage. For instance, a hospital may have a very high level of experience in organ transplants. This experience is acquired over a long period of time, that is, a hospital that has been providing organ transplantation services for many years can accumulate required knowledge and practical

skill. Knowledge and practical skill are the types of resources that cannot be imitated. Similarly, a health institution's abstract existence, the corporate culture, also develops over a long period of time, starting from the establishment stage, and this culture cannot be imitated by other institutions. The location of a health institution can also be considered as an institutional resource. A hospital may be built in a central, easily accessible, and densely populated area. Competitors may not be able to find a similar location or may have to pay a very high land price. In this case, the location will also provide the healthcare institution with an important competitive advantage.

- **Organization:** Possessing the resources listed above is not enough for a health institution to gain competitive advantage. To secure a competitive advantage, valuable, scarce, and hard-to-imitate resources must also be mobilized to take advantage of environmental

opportunities and protect against environmental threats. However, mobilizing resources requires the existence of certain institutional and administrative processes, that is, a well-established organizational arrangement. Valuable resources and capabilities can be used in service delivery processes through institutional and administrative processes such as official communication systems, administrative control systems, pricing policies, and inventory management.

Figure 4 describes the relationship between resources (VRIO) and sustainable competitive advantage. Sustainable competitive advantage can be defined as a health institution's ability to maintain an advantageous position over its competitors in the long run. A health institution can achieve sustainable competitive advantage by outperforming its competitors. That is, not just creating an advantage to begin with, but making this gain permanent is referred to as sustainable competitive advantage.

Figure 4. The Relationship between VRIO and Competitive Advantage

Source: Adapted from Barney and Clark, 2007:70.

VRIO analysis is a framework used to evaluate the resources and capabilities of an institution to determine whether they are valuable, rare, inimitable, and organized. In the context of VIRO analyses, we need ask the following questions to find out if the health institution's resources create sustainable competitive advantage:

- **The valuableness question:** Does the health institution's resources and capabilities enable it to protect against environmental threats and capitalize on opportunities?
 - **The rarity question:** Are the resources controlled by rival firms?
 - **The inimitability question:** Do other health institutions have to incur high costs to acquire or develop these resources and capabilities?
 - **The organization question:** Does the health institution's organizational structure and processes ensure the effective use of these resources and capabilities?

By examining the responses given to each of these questions, we can make inferences about the effects of resources on competitive advantage and the economic performance of the institution. For instance, if an institution's resources do not help it to take advantage of environmental opportunities, its competitive power will decrease. The decrease in competitive power will also negatively affect the institution's revenue and profitability. If a health institution's resources are valuable but not rare, it will not be able to gain a competitive advantage but will also not fall behind its competitors. Therefore, valuable but not rare resources reflect the strength side of the health institution. On the other hand, even though a health institution possesses valuable, rare, and not easily imitable resources, it may not be able to use them efficiently. In this case, the institution can have a temporary competitive advantage, but this advantage may not be long-lasting. Hence, for a health institution to achieve a sustainable competitive

advantage, it must not only have valuable, rare, and inimitable resources, but also be able to use them productively.

Competence analysis: the core competencies

The term "core competence" was first used by Prahalad and Hamel (1990). Core competence refers to a common learning process in the coordination of different production capabilities and integration of various technological enhancements. A core competence is a set of knowledge, skills, and experiences that are necessary to achieve a competitive advantage in a particular area. The quality of service provided by a health institution, the possession of qualified health personnel, or the use of advanced technologies should not be considered as a core competency. On the other hand, as compared to rivals, a heightened specialization of a hospital in organ transplants can be considered as a core competence. Core competencies can take various forms. For instance, a hospital's development and implementation of a new treatment method, providing medical services to patients arriving at the emergency room within 5 minutes, offering patient-centered services by all staff, employing qualified doctors, high staff personnel, high institutional prestige in the community are all different forms of core competencies. Simply put, core competency should be seen as the cohesive harmonization of institution-specific experiences, institution-specific services, institution-specific business forms (routines, procedures), institution-specific managerial resources (managerial experience, knowledge, and skills) and institutional culture.

Characteristics of Core Competencies

There are five basic characteristics of core competencies (Prahalad and Hamel, 1990; White, 2004: 247)¹⁸:

- **Benefit Creation:** Resources and activities that raise the level of perceived benefit for patients using the services provided form the core competency of the health institution. For example, a dialysis center can offer tablet computers, newspapers, and novels to patients to make them more comfortable, or organize social activities not posing health risks to patients to have them spend good time. Thus, dialysis patients will feel more benefit from the service they receive.

- **Inimitability:** Every institution has its own service delivery model, organizational structure, rules, procedures, values, history, and culture. Because the core competencies are created through the structure, procedures, values, culture, and past experiences of the institution, it is very difficult for other institutions to imitate core them.

- **Market Expansion:** Core competencies increase the value and benefit of the services provided by the institution. A high level of value and benefit in turn attracts patients from different regions. Thus, the health

institution will have the opportunity to expand its market share.

- **Durability:** Core competencies of a health institution should be long lasting. Short-term core competencies may provide temporary competitive advantage for the institution, but they do not contribute to the institution's sustainable competitive advantage.

- **Non-Replicability:** The effects or outcomes created by core competencies should not be replicable. Non-replicability and non-substitutability of core competencies are different concepts. Non-replicability of the core competencies is enough, outcomes obtained using these competencies (e.g., technical quality or customer satisfaction) must also be non-replicable.

Core Capabilities and Strategy

Health institutions must have basic or distinctive capabilities to gain a competitive advantage. Basic or distinctive capabilities are institution specific strengths that allow the institution to differentiate its services from those offered by rivals (Hill and Jones, 2010:74-76). The basic capabilities of health institutions refer to the resources the institution has and its ability to use these resources productively. First consider the presence of resources. The existence of a neurosurgeon is a must for all hospitals offering brain tumors treatment services because brain surgery operations cannot be performed without a neurosurgeon. Technological resources (e.g., operating room equipment) are also required for brain surgery. These resources are the minimum required resources for all hospitals offering these services. However, although possessing resources is a must, it is not sufficient to generate basic capabilities. Some resources may be specific to health institutions. For instance, a hospital may have a highly experienced specialist and gamma knife technology in the brain surgery department. Not all hospitals have qualified specialists and high-cost gamma knife technology. Resources owned by only one or a few health institutions are called "unique resources". Unique resources are resources that give a health institution a competitive advantage and cannot easily be obtained by competitors (Johnson, et al., Whittington, 2008:121). Therefore, unique resources can be seen as the basic or distinctive resources of a health institution.

A health institution's competencies refer to the processes and activities that enable it to effectively coordinate and utilize its resources. Capabilities are not pertinent to the resources per se, but rather they are about how the resources are used. Most hospitals have certain operational rules, procedures (such as patient admission procedure), and control systems. These rules, procedures, or systems define the minimum conditions required to provide service and shape the capabilities of the institution (Hill and Jones, 2010:101). Regardless of which specific hospital we go to, we are first

¹⁸ The first three characteristics were determined by Prahalad and Hamel (1990).

greeted and guided by public relations personnel. Obtaining informed consent before surgery is also a common practice for all hospitals¹⁹. The activities and procedures that a health institution carries out to provide service are considered as “minimum or general capabilities”. On the other hand, some capabilities are specific to the institution. For example, obtaining informed consent from the patient before the surgery is a basic procedure, while providing “professional psychological support” to comfort the patient before the surgery may be an institution specific service. In short, an institution specific capability is a resource or practice that a health

institution can use in a different and more efficient way from its competitors. The differences in capabilities among institutions are the underlying cause of performance variability with similar resources.

As described in Figure 5, the development of core/distinguishing capabilities requires both the availability of institution specific resources and their efficient and productive utilization (Hill and Jones, 2010:100; Ljungquist, 2007). Core capabilities are the skills to run the institution or manage a process differently from rival institutions.

Figure 5. Institutional Resources, Capabilities, and Skills

Source: Hill and Jones, 2010:108-109.

The relationship between strategy and core competencies is depicted in Figure 6. Core competencies contribute to the development of the health institution’s strategies. To develop realistic, feasible, and achievable strategies, first of all, the institution must thoroughly assess its competencies. It is because the core competencies draw the limits of what the health institution can do/achieve. For instance, a hospital manager may consider offering free chronic health screenings to individuals in elderly care homes or nursing homes in their area as part of a market penetration strategy. However, if the hospital does not have sufficient resources (e.g.,

medical-health personnel and mobile laboratory equipment), providing the health screening service will not be possible. Moreover, even if sufficient resources are available, if capabilities are lacking (e.g., absence of a concrete plan, program, and job description for the health screening personnel), the screening activity cannot be carried out. On the other hand, strategies can also be developed to create and enhance the necessary resources and capabilities to create core competencies. For example, the screening program can be planned and programmed by collaborating with a public health specialist or epidemiologist.

¹⁹ Informed consent is the process for obtaining patients’ consent prior to the treatment about their health statuses and procedures, such as the diagnosis made, the type of treatment and its success rate, the duration of the treatment, who will perform the operation, where, when and how will the operation

be performed, the risks and side effects of the treatment, alternative treatment methods, and the potential outcome if the treatment is not performed.

Figure 6. Strategy and Core Competencies

As shown in Figure 6, there is not a one-way linear relationship between core competencies and strategy, but rather there is a two-way relationship (Hill and Jones, 2010:102). Core competencies form the foundation for the development of strategies. According to Prahalad and Hamel, an institution's core competencies are like a window opened to future opportunities (Prahalad and Hamel, 1990). Therefore, institutions should take their core competencies into account to better position themselves in the market and achieve a competitive advantage. On the other hand, strategies also contribute to the generation of resources that set the ground for the emergence or strengthening of core competencies, and the development of capabilities.

Tasks of Managers

For the development of core competencies, managers must fulfill five basic tasks (Prahalad and Hamel, 1990):

i. Health institution managers should clearly and thoroughly define their core competencies and ensure all personnel understand them. The managers should also assess the institution's core competencies through a basic competency test. Basic competency test is conducted by answering questions on the three characteristics of core competencies discussed above (Gallon, et al., 1995):

- Does this competency generate more value and benefit for patients?
- Does this competency increase the number of potential patients, that is, does it expand the service area?
- Can this competency be easily copied?

Examples of sub-questions containing the details of these general questions are given Table 2.

Table 2.

Main and Sub-Questions on the Characteristics of Core Competencies

Main Questions	Sub-Questions
Does this competency generate value for patients?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are the services provided using this competency important for the institution? • Are the services provided using this competency consistent with the institution's goals? • Are the services provided using this competency cost efficient? • Do the services provided using this competency meet the patients' needs?
Does this competency expand the service area?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Are the services provided using this competency different-unique products in the market? • Are the services provided using this competency innovative? • Do the services provided using this competency make the institution stand out from the competitors in the eyes of patients?
Does this competency create competitive advantage?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Do the services provided using this competency enable the institution to provide services to different regions? • Is this competency used commonly within the institution?

Source: Adapted from Ljungquist, 2007.

ii. Healthcare facility managers should develop a plan (agenda) for acquiring core competencies and prepare a roadmap that demonstrates how existing and new competencies can strengthen the institution's position in the current or new market. Moreover, managers must identify areas (services) where current competencies are insufficient and areas (services) where new competencies are required.

iii. The history of the institution is a crucial factor in acquiring core competencies. It is because the institutions develop their core competencies over time using their own unique methods (Barney, 1986). This period can cover a span of five to ten years. Therefore, managers should focus and consistently strive to develop core competencies without losing motivation.

iv. Healthcare facility managers should ensure that core competencies are spread throughout all departments in a continuous but flexible manner.

v. Managers must constantly protect and defend core competencies. Over time, the importance given to core competencies may decrease due to reasons such as lost interest or implementation of cost-saving measures. Protecting and sustaining core competencies should be seen as the most important part of the chosen strategy.

Analysis of institutional functions: value chain

According to the value chain model developed by Porter (1985), an institution must create value to gain a competitive advantage. In general, value is defined as the amount of money that a customer (patient) is willing to pay for the perceived benefit of a product (service). The value that a product (service) provides to a firm (an institution) is defined as the difference between the revenue generated by the product (service) and the total monetary value of the inputs used to produce it (Porter, 1985:38). According to Porter, the sequence of activities that extends from the procurement of inputs to the delivery of products to users and after-sales services is classified as the value chain.

Porter and Teisberg (2006:3-5) point out that while competition is expected to lead to improvements in "quality" and lower "costs," these results have not occurred in the health sector. Therefore, they conceptualize the competition in the health sector as "zero-sum competition". Zero-sum competition results from health institutions competing in incorrect levels and on incorrect domains. Competition between institutions leads to decreased quality, increased costs, unused capacity, and higher management costs, which do not benefit the competing institutions, patients, or insurance companies. Porter and Teisberg (2006:4) suggest that competition between health institutions should be "positive, that is, competition should be based on "value created and enhanced for patients", rather than based on short-term cost reduction. The value for patients arises as an end product of the entire medical care process (including examination, laboratory tests, invasive procedures, etc.). The only thing that truly matters

to patients is not the type and level of services received (outputs), but the extent to which the care or treatment process improves their health. Of course, it is also necessary to achieve positive outcomes at as low a cost as possible. Hence, we can define value as obtaining the best outcomes for patients with minimum cost. Value-based strategies enable both improvement of service quality and reduction of service costs.

Health institutions that provide services that create value for patients will have the opportunity to attract more patients. Moreover, value-based competition will not only be beneficial for patients, but also for insurance companies. The main reason for failure of the cost control strategy by Social Security Institution (SSI) in Turkey in the form of price limits is the focus mainly on outputs rather than effects of the payment system. That is, the surge in health expenditures despite all cost-saving measures is attributable to the adoption of reimbursement plans that focus on output instead of value creation. Hospitals and other health institutions are forced to reduce the number of services provided to patients due to the increasing strictness of price restrictions. Under these conditions, it becomes more difficult for patients to receive desired treatments and benefits. Hence, if the insurance institutions work on a value creation-based payment plan rather than a fee-for-service or per case payment model, it will be more beneficial for the patients (Porter and Teisberg, 2006: 62-63).

Value and Outcome

The concept of value is pertinent to the final output and cost of the service provided. According to Porter and Lee, the primary task of managers is to increase the value of the services provided to patients, i.e., to try to achieve the desired output with minimum cost. To do this, managers must abandon the supply driven service delivery system and switch to a patient-centered service delivery system organized in line with patients' needs (Porter and Lee, 2013).

As value is defined as obtaining the desired output (desired improvement in the patients' health statuses) with minimum cost. We can algebraically formulate the value as follows:

$$\text{Value} = \text{Output} / \text{Total Cost}$$

The services offered, regardless of their extent and variety, will not have any value if they do not provide the desired results for patients (ultimate output=0). Although ultimate output is often interchangeably used with service quality, in essence, they are different concepts. Ultimate output is a general concept that includes quality. Ultimate output refers to the improvement in the health status of the patient, rather than the extent and variety of services offered. For example, "patients' satisfaction with the services received" is not the ultimate output; "the patients' level of satisfaction with their health statuses" is the ultimate output (Porter, 2010). Moreover, providing more service to the patient

does not necessarily mean that the ultimate output will be satisfactory. Therefore, managers should focus on ultimate output rather than the quantity of the service. Prominent scholars of the discipline emphasize that the

service delivery processes, and development and improvement of these processes are institutional tactics, and that they cannot replace ultimate outputs (Porter and Guth, 2012:27; Porter, 2010).

Figure 7. General Ultimate Output

The ultimate output includes all stages of the medical care process and reflects the improvement in the patient's health status. Patients are not concerned with the services or interventions provided to them, but rather with the overall outcomes of the care process (if they recovered totally, if their health statuses improved) (Porter and Guth, 2012:28). However, there is no single ultimate output reflecting a patient's health status. As it can be seen from Figure 7, there are multiple, multi-dimensional outcomes for each medical intervention in case of each disease. The overall ultimate output is the combination of outcomes from the entire care process. To be precise, each service or intervention has its own outcome, and thus, each outcome has a different weight on the overall ultimate output. Hence, the overall ultimate output can be calculated as a weighted sum of the outcomes of the entire medical care process:

Overall Ultimate Output = $\sum_{i=1}^n O_i W_i$,
 where O_i is the i th outcome, and W_i is the weight of i th outcome.

Examples of service or intervention outcomes include survival, gaining functional health status, and sustainability of treatment. When each stage of the medical care process produces the desired outcome, true benefit is created for the patient. As portrayed in Figure 8, Porter views ultimate output in health institutions in a three-tiered hierarchy.

Figure 8. The Three-Tiered Hierarchy of Ultimate Output in Health Institutions

Based on the three-tiered hierarchy of ultimate outcome measures related to two diseases and health output depicted in Figure 8, we provide examples of conditions in Table 3.

Table 3.

Examples of Outcome Measures		
Breast Cancer	Dimensions	Primary Acute Knee Osteoarthritis Requiring Prosthesis
Survival rate (1 year, 3 years, 5 years, over 5 years)	Survival	Mortality rate (Hospitalized patients)
	↕	
-Time to recovery -Functional state -Breast cancer prevention -Results of breast cancer prevention surgery	Degree of health or recovery	-Degree of functional state -Degree of pain -Degree of physical activity ability -Readiness to return to work
	↕	
Time to recovery	Time to recovery and time to return to normal activities	-Treatment period -Time to return to normal activities
	↕	
-Hospital infection -Nausea or vomiting -Febrile neutropenia -Restriction of mobility -Depression	Lack of benefit from care or treatment process (Diagnostic errors, ineffective treatment, treatment-related discomfort, complications, side effects)	-Pain -Length of stay -Infection -Pulmonary embolism -Deep vein thrombosis -Myocardial infarction -Urgent revision delirium

	↕	
-Recurrent cancer -Consequences of recurrent cancer -Sustainability of functional state	Sustainability of health or prevention and recurrences	-Sustainability of functional state - Ability to live independently - Need for revision or reoperation
	↕	
-Incidence of second primary cancer -Brachial plexopathy -Premature osteoporosis	Long term consequences of treatment (Treatment induced Diseases)	-Loss of mobility due to inadequate rehabilitation -Complex fracture risk -Susceptibility to infection -Knee stiffness due to an unknown complication -Regional pain syndrome

Value and Cost

The second dimension (component) of value in healthcare is the service costs. Reducing service costs lead to an increase in value, but care must be taken when reducing costs. Attempting to reduce costs without considering the outcomes of an intervention or service is a dangerous approach and can lead to unintended consequences (e.g., patient injury or death), as well as impede effective service delivery. Moreover, reduction in costs in a manner that poses danger to patients is not real cost savings but results in “illusory cost savings” (Porter and Guth, 2012:27). On the other hand, reducing service costs does not imply a decrease in the cost of each service provided to the patient. On the contrary, while it may seem like an upsurge in costs, increase in some services can lead to a reduction in total treatment costs by generating achievements such as early intervention, reduced medical errors, minimized complications, and prevention of disease recurrence. Hence, managers should focus on the total cost of medical care in their cost measurement or calculations, rather than on individual services provided.

Value creation chain

The value chain, developed by Porter (1985), is a model that outlines how value is generated. A health institution provides a wide variety of independent activities with a common goal. Examining the patients, providing diagnosis services, treatment of hospitalized patients, discharging treated patients, and monitoring the health status of the patients after discharge (follow-up exams) are typical examples of services a hospital produces and delivers. In addition to these typical services, a health institution performs administrative activities such as food provision, maintenance and repair, patient acceptance, procurement, and material provision. All these activities are referred to as the value chain. For a health institution to create more value than its competitors, it must consider all of its institutional activities in an integrated manner. The value chain model allows for a systematic analysis of the resources and activities of a health institution. The main purpose of the value chain analysis is to determine how to increase the value of services, that is, how to ensure the best outcomes in patient’s health status at the lowest

cost level. Increasing value enhances the competitiveness of the institution (Porter, 1985:33). The value chain model requires assessing and, if necessary, re-organization of the institutional activities to form a value chain. Every health institution has its own unique value chain. The value chains of institutions vary according to the history of the institution, the strategy chosen, and the way the strategy is implemented. The differences in value chain standards of institutions themselves in their competitive advantage potentials (Porter, 1985:36).

Health institutions are systems that convert inputs into outputs. Institutions are not just a random collection of personnel, machines, and materials. In order to be able to offer services that customers are willing to pay for, an institution must organize its personnel and other resources around systematically formed “activities”. According to Porter, each activity carried out in an institution should be seen as independent but inter-related production practices. The basic purpose of the value chain model is (i) to determine how and to how much each activity adds value to the services provided by the institution, and (ii) to estimate the cost of the activity. In deciding how to organize and coordinate activities, managers must take the value created by the activities and the costs incurred into account (Porter, 1985:39). By improving the organization of and coordination of activities, both the value of the services can be increased and the cost of the services can be reduced. In short, according to the value chain model, an institution’s competitive advantage depends on how effectively it carries out its activities and how efficiently it coordinates the relationships among its activities.

Porter (1985) argues that there are nine important activities that create value in an institution and divides these activities into two main groups: (1) primary activities and (2) support activities.

Primary Activities

Primary activities consist of activities pertained to the primary purpose of the institution, that is, the production and delivery of services. More precisely, primary activities involve procurement of inputs used in the service production process, utilizing these inputs in

the production of services, and provision of after treatment (Porter, 1985:37).

According to Porter's value chain model, primary activities comprise five activities, namely, input procurement, service delivery, distribution, marketing and sales, and after-sales services (Porter, 1985:39-40). We provide brief explanations of these activities below.

i. Input procurement

Input procurement activities basically cover activities related to the procurement process of inputs needed to provide services. Materials (drugs, medical supplies, and other consumables) requirements planning, storage of medical equipment, pharmaceutical products, and general consumables in warehouses, inventory (stock) control, protecting materials stored in warehouses, properly disposing of expired drugs and supplies, and timely delivery of drugs and medical supplies to service departments (such as inpatient services, operating rooms, intensive care units, etc.) are the main activities conducted in the input procurement process. Drug and medical supply expenses are the second highest spending category after personnel expenses in health institutions. Therefore, managers aiming to reduce service costs and increase productivity must be careful in timely procurement, protection, and efficient use (prevention of unnecessary use or waste) of drugs and medical supplies.

Health institutions' most important input is patients. Therefore, analyzing the served population and region (market), evaluating the health needs, performing market competitiveness analysis, determining the services offered, and carrying out promotion, advertising, and marketing efforts to attract patients can be considered as activities related to input procurement.

ii. Service Delivery

Health service delivery refers to activities conducted to transform inputs into outputs. The service delivery process starts with a patient's application to the institution. Health services offered by health institutions vary depending on their position in the comprehensive health system (such as primary, secondary, and tertiary levels). While a primary level health institution (e.g., a family health center) provides basic services such as outpatient examination, basic diagnostic services, and patient referral services, the secondary level health institution (e.g., a general hospital), in addition to examination and diagnostic services, offers more

complex services such as surgical and interventional services, and observation services.

iii. Distribution

Distribution activities are more applicable to manufacturing enterprises. The distribution activities in such businesses include storing manufactured products, taking delivery orders, preparing delivery plans, and transporting the products. On the other hand, in health institutions, examples of distribution activities involve patient discharge planning, discharge procedures, patient information during discharge, and free patient transportation services.

iv. Marketing and Sales

Marketing and sales activities include activities such as product and service promotion, advertising, sales, choice of distribution channels, and pricing. Specifically, patient satisfaction surveys, service quality evaluations, public relations, and advertising activities are also part of the marketing and sales activities in health institutions. Marketing activities in health institutions can be considered as part of the activities for attracting patients.

v. After-Sales Services

After-sales services refers to various processes which make sure an institution's customers are satisfied with its products and services after they purchase them. Examples of after-sales services are free shipment, installation, and setup, simple and fast maintenance and repair procedures, and the establishment of a wide service network. In case of health institutions, control check-ups performed after the patient is discharged, wound care and medical dressing services, monitoring of treatment by visiting the patient at home, discounted services for newborns in the hospital, and the distribution of free patient specific instruction brochure are examples of after-sales services.

Swayne et. al. (2006) stress that the basic role of health institutions is health services delivery, and therefore, focus on three primary activities these institutions carry out, namely, activities carried out before service delivery (pre-service activities), activities carried out during service delivery (point-of-service activities), and activities carried out after service delivery. These primary activities and their sub-activities are listed in detail in Figure 9 below.

Figure 9.

Source: Adapted from Michael E. Porter, *Competitive Advantage: Creating and Sustaining Superior Performance* (New York: Free Press, 1985), p. 37.

Value chains are made of primary activities. We provide a detailed description of value chain in terms of primary activities, and their sub activities in table 4 below.

Table 4.

Descriptions of Value Chain Components

Value Chain Component	Description
<i>Service Delivery</i>	The activities in the value chain that are directly involved in ensuring access to, provision of, and follow-up for health services
<i>Pre-Service</i>	
• Market/Marketing Research	Determine the services that create value prior to the actual delivery of health services, determine appropriate target market
• Services offered/ Branding	Information dissemination to present and prospective patients and other stakeholders regarding the range and location of available services
• Pricing	Charge schedule for available services
• Promotion	Activities that ensure all the elements needed to deliver health services are available at the appropriate place at the appropriate time
• Distribution/Logistics	Activities and systems that facilitate patient/customer entry into the service delivery system, including appointments and registration
<i>Point-of-Service</i>	
• Clinical Operations	Those service delivery activities that create value at the point where services are actually delivered
• Quality	The activities that convert the human and nonhuman resources into health services
• Process Innovation	Actual provision of health services to the individual patient
• Marketing	Activities and groups of activities that are designed specifically to improve the quality and quantity of health services
• Patient Satisfaction	Activities to offer new products, seek new customers, provide better services delivery, and cause services to be perceived as higher value
<i>After-Service</i>	
• Follow-up	Activities that create value after the patient has received the health services
• Clinical	Activities designed to determine the effectiveness of or the patient's satisfaction with health services received
• Marketing	Activities that assist in determining what other services need to be delivered
• Billing	Value creating activities that ensure more understandable and efficient billing procedures
• Follow-on	
• Clinical	Activities that facilitate entry into another value chain (from hospital to home care, etc.)
• Marketing	
<i>Support Activities</i>	The activities in the value chain that are designed to aid in the efficient and effective delivery of health services
<i>Organizational Culture</i>	
• Shared Assumptions	The overarching environment within which the health services organization operates
• Shared Values	The assumptions employees and others share in the organization regarding all aspects of service delivery (e.g., needs of patients, goals of the organization)
• Behavioral Norms	The guiding principles of the organization and its employees. The understandings people in the organization have regarding excellence, risk taking, etc. Understandings about behavior in the organization that can create value for patients
<i>Organizational Structure</i>	
• Function	Those aspects of the organization structure that are capable of creating value for customers/patients
• Division	Structure based on process or activities used by employees (e.g., surgery, finance, human resources)
• Matrix	Major units operate relatively autonomously subject to overarching policy guidelines (e.g., hospital division; outpatient division; northwest division)
	Two-dimensional structure where more than a single authority structure operates simultaneously (e.g., interdisciplinary team with representatives from medicine, nursing, administration)
<i>Strategic Resources</i>	
• Financial	Value creating financial, human, information resources, and technology necessary for the delivery of health services
• Human	Financial resources required to provide the facilities, equipment, and specialized competencies demanded by the delivery of health services
• Information	Individuals with the specialized skills and commitment to deliver health services
• Technology	Hardware, software, and information processing systems needed to support the delivery of health services
	The facilities and equipment required to provide health services

Support Activities

Support activities include activities that facilitate or support the implementation of the primary activities. However, while the infrastructure of the institution does not directly relate to any primary activity, it constitutes the backbone of the entire value chain (Porter, 1985: 38). Support functions are summarized below (Porter, 1985: 39):

i. Procurement

The procurement activities refer to the purchasing of the resources needed by the health institution. Procurement is an activity carried out by all departments of the institution. That is, while some materials are purchased by the central procurement department, some materials can be purchased directly by the departments. The efficacy of the procurement activities directly affects the quality and cost of the purchased inputs. Quality of inputs has a direct and significant impact on the patients' safety and service quality. Furthermore, procurement is closely related to service costs. To reduce service costs, high-quality inputs must be purchased in

the most economical way. An efficient procurement process can facilitate the institution's primary and support activities to create more value through enabling the institution to improve the quality and lower the cost of the services it produces. However, value creation requires the procurement process to prioritize the quality of inputs over their costs. It is because purchasing high-quality inputs at a high cost will create more value than purchasing low-quality inputs at a low cost. Although the cost of services provided using low-quality inputs may be low, the actual cost may be higher when considering the costs arising from negative outcomes such as recurrent diseases, re-surgeries, prolonged treatment and resulting rise in average length of stay, and serious side effects.

The procurement process is not limited to the purchase of inputs. It requires developing beneficial relationships with suppliers. Constructing and maintaining long-term strategic cooperation with the supplier institutions can facilitate increasing value in the health institutions.

ii. Technology Development

Technology development refers to the design of new products, services, and service delivery processes. Technology includes not only the machinery, tools and equipment, and methods, but also the "knowledge resources" used in production activities (Daft, 2000: 258). Technology development aims not only to make the services offered different than and superior to those of competitors, but also to reduce the cost of the services.

iii. Human Resource Management

Human resource management performs activities pertaining to the employment (recruitment, selection, placement), development (performance evaluation, in-service training, career management), compensation (job evaluation, determining wages and bonuses), and integration (job health, complaints, union relations) of employees. Almost all services in health institutions are provided by health professionals. The knowledge, skills, and motivation of personnel are the most important factors that determine the quality of service. Therefore, human resources should be seen as the most important strategic input that adds the most value to institutional activities.

iv. Infrastructure

Infrastructure refers to institutional culture, management system, and organizational construct. Therefore, activities pertaining to the establishment and management of the institutional culture, development of management systems (planning, leadership, control, etc.), and design of the institutional structure are infrastructural activities.

As discussed above, each primary activity consists of independent sub-activities. These sub-activities can also be classified as direct activities, indirect activities, and quality assurance (QA) activities (Porter, 1985:43-44). Direct activities are value-adding activities. For example, activities such as diagnosing illnesses in hospitals, developing an appropriate treatment plan, and providing surgical services are directly value-adding activities. Indirect activities are activities that facilitate the directly value-adding activities. Keeping patient records organized, maintaining the cleanliness of clinics, performing periodic maintenance on laboratory equipment, and training the personnel are examples of indirect activities. Quality assurance activities cover activities carried out to realize the institution's established quality standards. Process control, checking infection control measures, and controlling the temperature and taste of food offered to patients are just a few examples of activities performed under quality assurance.

Margin

The concept of margin is related to value creation and cost in an institution. Therefore, margin is located at the end of value chain in Figure 10. As mentioned above, value refers to the amount customers are willing to pay for the benefit they obtain from the services of the institution. In this sense, value can be considered as the institution's total revenue. Cost refers to the total costs incurred (sum of the costs of all the activities described above) to provide the services (create value). The margin is the difference between the total value created and the total cost. If the total value created by an institution (total revenue) is higher than the total cost incurred, the institution will make a profit (Porter, 1985:38).

Figure 10. General Value Creation Chain

Perormans analysis

Quality

From a marketing perspective, the concept of quality can be defined as “meeting customer expectations”. This definition focuses on the customers’ experiences and perceptions. In this sense, for a service to be considered of high quality, it must satisfy customers’ needs. This approach to quality is also widely accepted in quality studies conducted in Turkey. However, despite its wide acceptance, this approach overlooks the scientific-technical aspect of medical care. In general, patients have limited options in making choices regarding medical care they need. On the other hand, customers may have a wide range of alternatives in other service sectors such as accommodation and food sectors. In the medical care sector, patients can only observe the care environment (cleanliness, noise, bureaucracy) and the behavior of health professionals. However, making a quality assessment based on these observations may lead to incorrect results (Kavuncubaşı and Esatoğlu, 1998). Furthermore, if the patients’ expectations are very low, meeting these expectations does not prove that the service provided is of high quality.

From a technical perspective, service quality can be measured by the improvement in the patient’s health status. In this sense, the concept of quality can be defined as the degree of compliance of the service provided with scientific standards. However, technical quality measure may be inadequate in terms of achieving the quality goal of the health institution if a service does not meet the patient’s psychological expectations.

A third approach to quality is the synthetic approach developed by Vincent K. Omachonu (1990). The synthetic quality approach considers both the technical (compliance with scientific norms and standards) and artistic (meeting customer expectations) dimensions of quality. According to this approach, the quality of health services is determined by technical quality

and the art of treatment (practical art). Taylor (1994) formulates the quality of health services as follows:

Quality of Healthcare Services = Technical Quality + Art of Treatment.

In this formulation, the technical aspect of quality includes the conformity of diagnostic and treatment services to contemporary medical science and scientific standards and norms; the artistic aspect also includes meeting the patient’s expectations for the services provided (John, 1991; Wilson, 1994). Scientific standards and norms are determined by universities, professional organizations, and research and development institutions. Scientific norms also involve common views on inputs used in the health service delivery process. Scientific norms are also referred to as normative criteria (Smith and Kaluzny, 1975:225).

One of the most important approaches to evaluating the technical quality of the services is the Structure-Process-Outcome approach developed by Donabedian. This approach contains three elements, and hence it is referred to as the three-element approach (Donabedian, 1980: 80-85; Donabedian, 1966, Donabedian 1995).

Structure includes the general characteristics of the health institution. The structure of the institution has a significant impact on its performance. The main elements of the structure are:

- i. the material resources of the health institution (building, equipment-technology, capital, and service units),
- ii. the human resources of the health institution (number and quality of personnel), and
- iii. the organizational structure of the health institution (medical services organization, management style, committees, type of clinical supervision).

The process factor is production-oriented and focuses on activities performed during the production and

delivery of services. The process factor includes activities such as examining the patient, diagnosing the disease, recommending an appropriate treatment plan, and executing it. Outcome expresses the impact of the services on the health status of patients. If the services provided have resulted in the desired change in the patient's health status, then the service outcome is considered as good.

According to the three-element approach, technically high-quality service can be achieved through the interaction of these three elements. A good structure (qualified personnel and advanced equipment) leads to the emergence of a good process (correct diagnosis and effective treatment), and a good service process ensures the attainment of desired outcomes. In order to evaluate the technical quality of a service, it is not enough to analyze each of these three elements independently; the relationships between the elements must also be taken into account (Donebedian, 1995).

Productivity

Productivity, in its simplest sense, describes the relationship between inputs and outputs, and is measured by comparing outputs to inputs. Sahney and Warden (1989:30) argues that the definition of productivity as the ratio of output to input is narrow and defines it as the quality, timing, and cost-effectiveness in achieving organizational goals. In this sense, productivity is not solely dependent on the physical outputs of the system. In other words, even if the amount of output produced does not change, increasing the quality of the output will also increase productivity.

Productivity measures how well an institution utilizes its existing resources. In a broader sense, productivity is the relationship between the output produced by a production or service system and the inputs used to create this output. Therefore, productivity can be defined as "the best use of resources in the production of various goods and services" (ILO, 1992:3; Kısa, 1999:15).

It is possible to classify the methods used to measure productivity in health institutions into three main groups, namely, ratio analysis, regression analysis, and data envelopment analysis.

Financial Performance

Another important institutional performance measure that should be focused on in the analysis of the internal environment of an institution is financial performance. Financial resources refer to the money, funds, or capital (Ağırbaş, 2014:18; Kavuncubaşı 2022:206-208). Since, financing is the provision of the institution's financial needs under appropriate conditions, financial management refers to activities pertaining to obtaining and effectively utilizing financial resources.

Value Creation: The financing not only serves the purpose of obtaining and using financial resources under favorable conditions but also contributes to the value of services by helping to improve the quality and reduce the costs of services (Fleming, Boles, 1994: 11-17; Kavuncubaşı 2022:206-208). There is a two-way interaction between value creation and financial performance (Fleming, Boles, 1994: 11-17; Kavuncubaşı 2022:206-208). Financially successful institutions tend to have better results in terms of service quality, patient safety, patient experiences, and re-admission rates (Ecninosa, Bernard, 2005: 60-72; Akinleye, McNutt, Lazariu, McLaughlin, 2019; Bazzoli, Clement, Lindrooth, Chen, Aydede, Braun, Loeb, J2007; Kavuncubaşı 2022:206-208). It is because financially sound institutions allocate more resources to improve quality by way of renewing infrastructure and investing in new technologies. Conversely, institutions with poor financial performance try to improve operational productivity by cutting spending on quality improvement efforts. To reduce costs to increase operational productivity, institutions resort to reducing staffing levels (especially nursing staff), cutting spending on investments in new technologies, and lowering service standards. Reducing staffing levels creates serious quality problems. For example, reducing the number of nurses leads to an increase in the number of patients per nurse, which in turn leads to an increase in the frequency of death rates, infection rates, and other unwanted medical outcomes (Kane, Shamlan, Mueller Duval, S., Wilt, J. T., 2007: 25-44; Kavuncubaşı 2022:206-208). In summary, hospitals struggling with financial difficulties try to survive by reducing service quality (Dong, 2015; Kavuncubaşı 2022:206-208).

Determining Strengths and Weaknesses: Information about the current financial situation of the institution and predictions about the future financial state are needed in the development of the institution's strategies. To understand the current financial situation and develop future predictions, the financial performance of the institution must be analyzed. Financial statements such as balance sheets and income statements are used to measure and evaluate financial performance. Financial performance analysis can reveal the institution's strengths and weaknesses by demonstrating how effectively the institution is using its financial resources.

A financially successful institution is one that can finance its resources at the desired levels and can provide balanced funding through both debt and equity. Financial performance analysis is an analytical process that uses financial and operational data to assess the financial health of the institution and evaluate the return and risk of investments. Thus, financial performance analysis helps management to assess the past investment projects and future investment potentials, enable a better financial planning/decision-making (Özgülbaş, 2005:125-144, Kavuncubaşı 2022:206-208). Financial performance analysis is also used to evaluate resource allocation decisions. Financial performance analysis is carried out using financial statements such as balance

sheets and income statements. Financial performance analysis includes the calculation and interpretation of financial performance indicators. Financial performance indicators can be compared with other institutions' figures and the sector's indicators to evaluate the institution's position relative to other institutions (Akar, 1992; Ağırbaş, 2014:74-99; Akça, İkinci, 2014:111-126; Kavuncubaşı 2022:206-208).

Financial performance indicators measure the financial health of an institution. The most used financial performance indicators are liquidity ratios, measuring the ability to meet short-term obligations; solvency ratios, indicating the long-term financial stability outlook; activity ratios, measuring the efficiency of using assets to generate revenue; and profitability ratios, measuring the ability to generate profits. By comparing these indicators with the industry standards and competitor's figures, an institution can assess its relative financial performance and identify its strengths and weaknesses.

Technical Performance

Analysis of Information Systems

Another area of focus in internal environment analysis is the institution's information systems. Information system refers to the construct facilitating the collection, storage, processing and analyzing data, reporting the findings of data analysis, and enabling the communication and synchronization among units. Information systems consist of information and communication technologies (servers, computers, wireless devices, etc.), database management, and software management. Compared to the past, information systems are increasingly utilized today to perform and control clinical and administrative activities. It is almost impossible to find a unit or desk without a computer in today's health institutions. Almost all employees in the institutions perform most or a significant part of their work using computers and communication technologies.

Health institutions' information systems can be divided into four main categories, namely, clinical information systems, operational information systems, strategic decision support systems, and electronic networks and e-health (smart and digital health) applications (Glandon, Smaltz, Slovensky, 2008:20-21; Kavuncubaşı 2022:208-212).

i. Clinical Information Systems

Clinical information systems support service delivery processes and help physicians and other service providers to make clinical decisions more effectively. Examples of clinical information systems include electronic patient records, nursing information systems, pharmacy information systems, laboratory information systems, imaging and radiology information systems, operating room information systems, medical educa-

tion and research information systems, patient monitoring systems, blood bank information systems, and clinical decision support systems.

ii. Operational Information Systems

Operational information systems consist of operational transaction systems and office automation systems. Operational information systems facilitate the improvements in institutional activities. Operational information systems are used for data entry, standard calculations, preparation of standard reports, internal communication (e.g. e-mail, video conferencing system, etc.), and operational control. Accounting records, personnel payrolls, outpatient appointment processes, stock control, invoicing, personnel start-of-work procedures are also carried out with operational information systems.

iii. Strategic Decision Support Systems

Strategic decision support systems are designed to assist top-level managers in the processes of strategic planning, managerial control, performance management, and outcome measurement. These systems integrate operational and clinical information with information obtained from the external environment (epidemiological data, competitor activities) to support managers in making strategic-level decisions.

iv. Electronic Networks and e-Health

Health institutions communicate electronically with insurance institutions, the Ministry of Health, and other health organizations for the purpose of data sharing. Receiving provisions, sending service bills, and sending patient statistics to the Ministry are carried out through electronic networks. The strengthening of the internet infrastructure also contributes to the change of service delivery methods. E-health applications (e.g., telemedicine) have become a strong alternative to the traditional service delivery models.

Analysis of Information Systems and Determination of Strengths and Weaknesses

It is possible to measure the strengths and weaknesses of an institution through its information system. Factors that positively affect the success of the information system are considered as the strength of the institution, while those that have negative impact on the success of the information system are considered as the weakness of the institution. A comprehensive model that constructs a causal relationship between the system structure and its outcomes is needed to measure the success of information systems. The DeLone and McLean Information Systems Success Model is one of the comprehensive models used to measure the success of information systems (DeLone, McLean, 2003: 9-30; Seddon, 1997: 240-253; Kavuncubaşı, Yıldırım, Tekeş, 2019: 60-66; Kavuncubaşı 2022: 208-212).

Conclusion

The main aim of internal environment analysis is to determine the strengths of health institutions required to achieve competitive advantage against rival health institutions, and to identify and alleviate the weaknesses. Moreover, the information about the strengths and weaknesses obtained through the internal environment analysis can be used to support the process of determining and evaluating institutions' strategies. The internal environment of a health institution is a set of factors that are under the control of management, but directly affect the success of the institution. To easily perform an internal environment analysis, it is necessary to divide a health institution into functional sub-systems and to analyze these sub-systems first individually and then in relation to other sub-systems. Finally, health institutions must take their current and potential resources into account to develop implementable and evidence-based strategies.

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